

TYPES OF LEARNERS AND THEIR TEACHING METHODS

Student of the Urgench State University named after Abu Rayhon Beruni
Otajonova Ug'iljon Habibullo Qizi

ANNOTATION

This article provides information about part of the "Types of Learners", their characteristics, the method of mastering a subject and the weaknesses of students belonging to this type. It can be used as a guide for every teacher. It describes the knowledge and skills of students and the methods through which they can fully master the subject.

Learner—is an individual who is willing to learn and understand new things. Learning is a process of understanding and concepts. An individual can be a learner at any point of the time they want. Factors like age, gender, etc. Do not come in between the learning of the learner. Learning depends on various measures like the need of paradigm shift skills required for a job, schooling requirements, or merely the curiosity or wishes of an individual. There are 4 types of learners. Understanding learning styles:

Visual

Auditory

Reading/Writing Preference

Kinesthetic

Kinesthetic learning links the process of learning to physical activity. It is a learning style during which the learner has to feel or move in order to learn more effectively. Also referred to as "tactile", "hands-on", or "physical" learning, Kinesthetic learning is part of three other main learning styles: Visual, auditory, and read and write. After establishing Kinesthetic learning, let's move on to a kinesthetic learner definition. Kinesthetic learners use body movement and interact with their environments when learning. To better understand something, they need to touch or feel it; hence practical information is usually preferred over theoretical concepts. A kinesthetic learning experience can be that of learning how to skate – but deep learning occurs when you are physically involved and start "doing" it. A kinesthetic learner would rather perform physical activity to learn something, as an activity participant, instead of passively listening to a lecture or watching a demonstration. That is why the best way of learning something new is by having your hands-on those things you are trying to learn. Kinesthetic learners may learn easier in classes that incorporate practical examples into the curriculum rather than through lectures. Kinesthetic learners retain information by doing, rather than (only) by seeing or listening. When they engage in some physical activity during learning, that's when you can expect the best learning outcome. From an early age, they will show interest in building sets; and they will often tear things apart in order to learn more about them. When a child wants to touch and hold something they are interested in rather than look at it, most probably they are kinesthetic learners. Some typical kinesthetic learners. Some typical kinesthetic learner characteristics include:

- Understand more when learning through hands-on experience
- Tend to get bored in traditional classroom
- Learn through movement
- Like to build things and work with their hands

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- Think more clearly when able to move
- Tend to need frequent study breaks to keep focus
- Prefer making posters or charts for group projects rather than gathering information and their benefits are :
 - Cognitive development;
 - Increased comprehension through physical activity;
 - Social skills development;
 - Stronger creative thinking;
 - Better problem solving ;
 - Better observation

Kinesthetic learners make up just 10 percent of population and are a bit more complex than other types of learners.

Strengths of kinesthetic learners:

Have excellent hand—eye coordination and agility

Easily remember how to do tasks a second time after doing them once.

Have great timing.

Be enthusiastic and boisterous.

Enjoy playing games with other.

According to research, the main problem of kinesthetic learners is understanding some subjects. For example, essay writing can pose difficulties because students can feel bogged down in so many words and ideas with nothing (physically) concrete to work with. Another problem is difficulty focusing on for long periods of time. Kinesthetic learners are not great at sitting atill and listening or reading for a long period of time. They crave physical activity . Math subject can be difficult for kinesthetic students above fourth grade. Since it is a science that consists mainly of numbers and concrete thoughts, they do not physically act and cannot imagine. Bodily kinesthetic intelligence is the capacity to manipulate objects and use a variety of physical skills. This intelligence also involves a sense of timing and the perfection of skills through mind—body union. Athletes, dancer, surgeons and crafts people exhibit well—developed bodily kinesthetic intelligence .

So, how can help teacher to kinesthetic learner in math subject?

By incorporating kinesthetic activities during lecture time. Using cards, computer activities, dice, marbles, dominoes fake money and coins to count units, physical clocks to tell time, and anything else that can translate abstract mathematical operations will be very useful methods. Essay writing can be difficult for kinesthetic children. As a solution, teach them to write texts on easy and small to pictures first. For example, give them a list of words used in the text and ask them to make a card from these words and use them in the text. They appreciate creative and practical work, and they may become interested in text and essay writing. There are some teaching strategies for kinesthetic learners:

- Let kinesthetic learners help out around the classroom. Allow these students to get up and move by passing out papers, writing on the board, etc
- Have creative time. While you read or show a video to students, allow them to doodle, color, work on a project or craft. This movement and hands—on work will help these types of students retain their information.

- Hold laboratory or experiments. Science, history and even math can have fun, engaging projects that allow kinesthetic learners to get active and be hands—on in their learning.
- Give students work to do while you lecture. Give students a worksheet to fill out, a specific way to take notes or even a map to color while you are lecturing. This will help kinesthetic learners retain information and ideas.
- Be animated in your teaching, for example sing, dance and be loud – use lots of energy. This increases their interest in the lesson.
- Encourage trial and error. Praise or any kind of encouragement increases the student's respect and interest in science. It is appropriate to give them easy and physical tasks for their errors.

In short, knowing your primary learning style is crucial for successful learning. This article went through one of the four main learning types—kinesthetic learning. By including the kinesthetic learning definition, its characteristics, and benefits, we provided a general understanding of this learning style in order to help you identify.

Whether you are a kinesthetic learner or not. This article can help you understand your students, identify your kinesthetic learners in your class and use the strategy list we provided, consisting of various teaching methods for kinesthetic learners.

Kinesthetic learning encourages physical activity, bolsters cognitive, social and emotional development, enhances the brain's capacity to retain information, and develops not just one's individual capacities and strengths, but also one's self—confidence in those capacities